

FROM SILOS TO STRATEGY: ALIGNING WEB ARCHIVING AND DIGITAL PRESERVATION

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Abstract - The management, curation, and preservation of digital collections increasingly includes content collected from the Web as well as digitised and other born-digital materials. This panel seeks to explore 1) to what extent these collections are managed by the same internal workflows and business processes, 2) to what extent content collected from the Web is included as part of an overall institutional digital strategy, and 3) in what areas do interconnections between web archive specialists and curators and digital preservation teams already exist or would be beneficial.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Web archives are among the youngest and fastest-growing born-digital collections in heritage organisations. Due to their unique nature, web archiving is often not fully integrated into standard digital preservation workflows and is typically organised separately from the processing of digitised and printed materials. Differences in national legislation also shape how web archives are collected and accessed. This panel will explore how web archiving and preservation activities align (or diverge) within institutions, the extent to which web collections are included in overarching digital strategies, and where stronger connections between curation and preservation would be beneficial. Drawing on over 20 years of combined experience in web archiving and preservation, the panellists will

share lessons learned and open the discussion for broader debate.

II. KB, NATIONAL LIBRARY OF THE NETHERLANDS

Starting in the late 1990s, the KB, National Library of the Netherlands, was one of the pioneers in digital preservation, conducting groundbreaking research and operationalising long-term preservation of digital content by 2002. Web archiving began in 2007 [1], first through pilots and projects, and later as a small activity compared to the Library's primary focus on digitization and printed material.

Over the past twenty years, organisational shifts have repeatedly moved preservation and web archiving in and out of focus, at times challenging the continuity of these tasks [2]. Traditional business unit structures also reinforced silos between web harvesting, archiving, QA, access, research, and mainstream ingest and preservation. To address this, the KB adopted a twofold strategy around 2020: first web archiving was recognized as a key activity in our collection strategy [3], second a horizontally structured agile web archiving team was established, bringing together software developers, curators, information analysts, preservation officers and a product owner. Positioned across multiple business units, including digital preservation, this team created both focus and organisational capacity for web archiving, while avoiding isolation. This model, once a novel experiment, has since become a template for other agile teams at the KB. The next step is to fully embed web archiving into the Library's

mainstream business processes, while maintaining the flexibility for ongoing development and innovation.

III. NATIONAL LIBRARY OF NEW ZEALAND

At the National Library of New Zealand, web content is collected through two distinct approaches: ongoing selective web archiving and an annual whole-of-domain harvest. While web archiving activities are distributed across different parts of the Library, the technical aspects are concentrated within the digital preservation team. This team is responsible for developing and maintaining the web archiving tools, facilitating the ingest of selective web archives into the Rosetta-based preservation repository, and overseeing the acquisition of the whole-of-domain harvest.

Despite this technical integration, the two streams of web content are managed differently. Selective web archives are treated as part of the Library's wider digital collections and receive the same preservation attention and curatorial oversight. In contrast, the whole-of-domain harvest—due to its scale—is not yet fully integrated into the Library's digital preservation workflows. Recent initiatives, including a revised digital preservation policy and an ongoing storage migration project, are prompting the Library to reconsider how whole-of-domain content could be more fully incorporated into a unified digital preservation framework.

IV. ROYAL DANISH LIBRARY

In the Royal Danish Library, the web archiving activities and the other digital activities have traditionally been organised quite separately. Just recently, in 2025, the developers of the library have been reorganised into agile product teams, and this has brought together web archiving with the development and operation of other born-digital workflows for newspapers, radio, and television, among other types of materials. This allows the developers and the curators to think across previous silos.

On the technical side, web archives remain separate from the rest of the Library's digital collections. They are the only collection not included — and not planned to be included — in the central preservation repository for metadata. This reflects the fundamentally different nature of web archives,

where content is preserved as-is, without control over formats, metadata, or structure, unlike other collections where these can be defined, checked, and validated. At the lowest preservation level, however, both the web archive and other digital collections share the same bit-level infrastructure, using the open-source bitrepository.org software. This ensures consistent control, monitoring, and execution of bit preservation across all digital holdings.

V. CONCLUSION

The preservation of digital heritage has matured, becoming embedded in organisational policy, strategy, and structure. In contrast, web archiving is still often viewed as a newer, more experimental activity, operating somewhat apart from core business processes. Recent developments show growing alignment between web archiving and preservation at both policy and organisational levels, though this integration remains less defined compared to mainstream library services.

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